

Cure multiphysic couplings effects on the dynamic behaviour of a thick epoxy

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Keywords: FEM, curing, epoxy, property gradients, laser induced shock wave.

1. General Introduction

High performance epoxies are more and more used for structural applications, namely for naval and offshore structures as well as for aeronautical and aerospace structures. It is well known today that internal residual stresses are developed during the curing of thermosetting materials. However, several defects like cracks and bubbles inside of the matter might arise, especially with increasing thickness. These defects may provoke serious damages within the concerned structure in service, especially under dynamic solicitations. In order to offer a better quality control, pulsed lasers have recently been used in non destructive inspection and characterization of composites [[1]]. This work focuses on internal gradients of properties generated during the curing and their consequences on the dynamical behavior of the epoxy matrix LY 556[®]. To do this, couplings induced by the curing between the chemistry, the thermal and the mechanics of the matrix in progress are presented and are taken into account for a spatial description within the epoxy matrix. This paper presents therefore simulation results for a 32 mm thick epoxy cylinder, exposed to laser induced shock waves, by taken into account internal gradients of properties induced by the curing.

2. The LY556 epoxy curing model

The resin system tested in this study is a three-component anhydride-epoxy system from Ciba. The blend consists of a bifunctional DGEBA-type epoxy (Araldite LY556, EEW=183-192 g/eq, n=0.3), a tetra-fonctionnal anhydride hardener (methyl-tetrahydrophthalic anhydride HY 917, anhydride equivalent weight = 166g/eq), and an accelerator (1-methyl imidazole DY 070). The components were mixed in LY 556/HY 917/DY 070 weight ratio of 100/90/1, resulting in a stoichiometric epoxy-anhydride mixture.

2.1. Kure kinetics

As the curing evolves, the chemical degree of conversion rate is less and less important and the thermosetting reaction becomes diffusion controlled [2]-[7]. Thus, a semi-empirical relationship (1) proposed by Fournier et al. [3], and based on free volume consideration, was chosen for the description of diffusion effects. Fournier et al. extended the Kamal and Sourour model [8] by a diffusion factor $f_d(\alpha)$ as presented by equation (1):

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = (K_1 + K_2 \alpha^m)(1-\alpha)^n f_d(\alpha), \text{ with} \quad (1)$$

$$f_d(\alpha) = \frac{2}{(1 + \exp[(\alpha - \alpha_f)/b])} - 1$$

Where $K_1 = A_1 \exp\left(\frac{-E_1}{RT}\right)$ and $K_2 = A_2 \exp\left(\frac{-E_2}{RT}\right)$.

α_f is the degree of conversion measured at the end of a given isothermal curing and b is an empiric diffusion constant of the material. This model fits the best experimental data for the cure kinetics of the LY556 epoxy resin as highlighted in Fig. 1. Impact of diffusion factor must therefore be taken into account.

The methodology for cure kinetics identification with diffusion effects is detailed in [9] and results are given in table 1 and 2.

The local temperature T of the matrix during the curing is defined by following equation of heat transfer:

$$\rho C_p \frac{dT}{dt} = - \text{div} \{ \lambda_T [-\text{grad } T] \} + r + \rho \Delta H^r \frac{d\alpha}{dt} - T \{ (3\lambda + 2\mu) \alpha_T \} \text{tr } \underline{\underline{\dot{\epsilon}}}^e \quad (2)$$

where C_p , λ_T , ρ and r stand respectively for specific heat, thermal conductivity, density and heat radiation imposed by the oven. α_T is the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) of the matrix in formation. λ and μ are the Lamé coefficients of the matrix.

Nevertheless, with increasing thickness, mass effect of the epoxy has to be taken into account because of the exothermal aspect of the thermosetting reaction. This statement is clearly demonstrated by equation of heat transfer (2) where the coupling between the thermal and the chemistry appears.

Precise details of the numerical solving strategy were presented by the author in a previous work [2]. This solving strategy was applied to a cylindrical block of resin (diameter 32 mm, height 30 mm) poured in a steel tube with a thickness of 6mm. The heating of the steel tube containing the liquid resin was reproduced by FEM analysis. A special attention was given to the determination of the convection interaction determination between the steel test tube and the air of the oven in order to reproduce as realistic as possible a real condition of oven heating that corresponds to a 3°C/min ramp followed by a 100°C plateau, for instance. Due to the axial symmetry of the structure the mesh was performed with 8-node thermally coupled axisymmetric solid, biquadratic displacement, bilinear temperature CAX8T elements of the Abaqus® element library. The full model requires 240 elements and 787 nodes for results convergence. The computation time takes around 25 min on a Pentium IV HT desktop at 3.20 GHz with 2Go of Ram.

3. Results for cure coupling effects on epoxy matrix state

The cure modeling approach was applied to the curing of a cylindrical block of resin (diameter 32 mm, height 30 mm).

3.1. Temperature and degree of cure history

The FEM solving technique led to the prediction of gradients of temperature developed within the matter during the cure, hence gradients of properties, which are significant as shown in Fig.1 for cure conversion and in Fig.2 for temperature history. Corresponding first internal elastic stress level observed was found around 10 MPa. which is significant at the hot stage of the curing, before the cooling step.

3.2. Properties gradients after the curing

It is assumed here that the thermal and chemical coupling problem is the main leading

coupling to take into account, as exposed in previous study [10]. Thus heat generated by the mechanics (contribution of strain rate, as mentioned in equation of heat transfer (2)) was considered as a second order effect. This assumption was validated by the solving of the thermal and chemical coupling only, presented in equation (2)[2], that fits well internal temperature history prediction during the curing as shown in Fig. 3.

Consequently, all mechanical parameters like Young modulus, bulk modulus, shear modulus, yield stress, failure stress could be considered as being dependent of degree of cure and temperature only.

3.2.1. Elastic modulus description

Elastic modulus E was deduced from shear modulus and Poisson ratio of the cured matrix that is supposed to be locally isotropic and homogeneous.

3.2.2. Elastic shear and bulk modulus G' and K

Shear tests were performed on pure epoxy matrix samples as shown in Fig. 4. The video controlled shear technique developed by [11] was used and led to the plot of local shear stress versus local strain.

Video controlled shear tests were performed at different temperature to account for rubbery or glassy state behaviors of the matrix. Results are shown in Fig. 5.

It is pointed out that elastic shear modulus was found to be around 10 MPa. in the rubbery state and increases strongly in the glassy state to a level of 1000 MPa. at room temperature. Thus, for a fully cured epoxy (~90% of degree of cure), shear modulus evolution versus temperature is summarized in Fig. 6.

A strong change is logically observed at T_g crossing. This sophistication was taken into account for the determination of G' obtained at the end of the hot stage before cooling, thanks to T_g modeling given by the T_g was calculated by the usual Pascault and Williams [[12]] relation (also called Di-Benedetto equation) relation as follows:

$$\frac{T_g - T_{g0}}{T_{g\infty} - T_{g0}} = \frac{\lambda\alpha}{1 - (1-\lambda)\alpha} \quad (3)$$

Where T_{g0} = -37.22°C, T_{g infinity} = 135.19°C, λ=0.57. Details are available in [2].

A linear mixture rule relation, based on the degree of conversion α , was used for G' modulus description as follows:

$$G'(\alpha, T) = (1 - \alpha) \cdot G'_{\text{liq}} + \alpha G'_{\text{fully cured}}(T) \quad (4)$$

Where elastic modulus in liquid state $G'_{\text{liq}} \sim 100\text{Pa}$. [[13]] and the fully cured modulus $G'_{\text{fully cured}}$ is given by Fig. 6.

The same linear mixture rule approach was applied to the bulk modulus K , but without any sophistication at T_g crossing assuming no changes there as exposed in [2].

After cooling to room temperature, the epoxy matrix is in a fully glassy state. However, degree of cure gradient exists within the matrix. Consequently gradient of shear modulus is developed as shown in Fig. 7.

3.2.1. Young modulus, Poisson ratio and density

Poisson ration was deduced from elastic shear and bulk moduli, assuming locally an isotropic behaviour. Density was deduced from the Li et al. Cure shrinkage model applied to the LY 556 epoxy, details are available in [13]. Young modulus was then calculated thanks to shear modulus and Poisson ratio and results are shown in Fig. 8.

3.2.2. Yield and failure stress description

Yield stress was obtained on a fully cured epoxy sample thanks to the video controlled shear tests presented in Fig. 6. It was then assumed that the yield stress evolution within the matrix, after return at room temperature, could be directly described by a linear dependency to the fully cured yield stress thanks to the local degree of conversion obtained after the curing. Evolution along the axis of the cylinder of epoxy is shown in Fig. 9

Failure stress is more delicate to model according to shear strain strain curves where plasticity clearly exists. Nevertheless, as the video controlled shear tests were conducted up to the macroscopic failure of the sample, fail stress given here stands for macroscopic failure stress. Failure stress was then described in the same manner as for yield stress and is presented in Fig. 10.

4. Oservation of thick LY556® epoxy by dynamic solicitations

The dynamic behavior of composites, submitted to impacts or blast waves, has been extensively studied

these last decades [14] particularly under laser induced shock wave [1], [15]. Some numerical works have been carried out by considering the composite material by an equivalent homogenous material, known as the Voight homogenization technique [17]. In other works, authors considered the composite material as a succession of plies in which the fiber direction can be specified but for which mechanical characteristics of the matrix (i.e. cured epoxy resin) are identical in each plies. Some authors even proposed some hydrodynamic shock data sets for ambient (after curing) epoxy resins under impact [18], [19], [21]. Recently Ecault et al have studied the dammage of epoxy under intense laser induced shock waves [20]. However, in the case of thick composites, the curing stage observed in section 3 shows non negligible evolution of the mechanical characteristics (Young modulus, density, yield stress, Poisson coefficient, ...) that vary along the sample thickness during and after the curing stage. In this section, numerical simulations, performed with the explicit finite element code RADIOSS®, point out differences of cured epoxy behaviour between homogenous and heterogeneous matrix released at ambient temperature, subjected to an hypothetic dynamic loading.

4.1. Dynamic loading

The loading temporal evolution chosen for this work is described in Fig. 11 and is supposed to generate a purely elastic wave like an ultrasonic loading such as the one used in non destructive inspection. However, The duration is artificialy increased to 1 μs since a shorter pulse would have required much more elements and so, a much longer computation time. Nevertheless, it still represents a possible physical pulse. The interest of this approach is to predict the ability of ultrasounds experiments of evaluating mechanical characteristics of cured resins. The solicitation is defined as a pressure profile in the most cured side. The maximum pressure reaches 7 MPa. Such a pulse can be obtained by impact experiments, laser induced shock waves, plate impacts or hopkinson bars.

In the present work, two loaded areas have been used, both are disks of 1.5 mm and 3 mm of radius, respectively.

4.2. Samples definition

In a first approach, samples are defined as a 3 cm thick column of 3D cubic elements along the z axis

(epoxy cylinder axis). Pressure is applied on the upper facet (most cured) and side nodes are blocked in x and y directions. In order to check the mesh influence, two mesh sizes have been chosen, respectively 500 and 5000 elements. The resituted pressure on the first element and the material velocity of nodes on the free surface (in vis a vis of the loaded surface) are monitored as simulation outputs. These two features are data that can be experimentally obtained by pressure gage for the first one [27] and by laser doppler velocimetry for the second one [25], [26]. In this first attempt, the sample is considered as homogeneous. The mechanical behaviour of the ambient material is given by a perfect elasto-plastic model, self consistent for describing the elastic stage. This model is governed by the yield stress Y_0 , the Young modulus E and the Poisson coefficient ν . In a column of density ρ_0 , the longitudinal wave velocity C_L is given by equation (5) :

$$C_L = \sqrt{\frac{E}{\rho_0}} \quad (5)$$

This behaviour is completed by a hydrodynamic behaviour composed of the Mie-Grüneisen equation of state (6) in which the reference state under dynamic compression is given by the Hugoniot equation of state (7 and 8):

$$\sigma = -P + \sigma_{dev} \quad (6)$$

with $P = \sum a_i \mu^i$ where $i \leq 3$ and a_i are material coefficients computed with (7) and (8) and $\mu = 1 - \rho/\rho_0$.

$$P - P_{ref} = \frac{\Gamma_0}{\rho_0} (e - e_{ref}) \quad (7)$$

$$D = C_0 + s(u - u_0) \quad (8)$$

Where the subscript $_{ref}$ refers for the reference state, the subscript $_0$ refers for the initial state, P is the hydrodynamic pressure, e the internal energy, Γ_0 is the Grüneisen coefficient, D the shock velocity, C_0 the bulk sound velocity and s a Hugoniot coefficient and u the material velocity.

The above constitutive law coupled with the above equation of state is able to describe the behaviour of the epoxy in elastic regime as well as in plastic (moderate shock) and hydrodynamic regime (intense shock). However, since the matter tackled in this article is the non destructive characterisation,

solicitations will be considered below the yield stress Y_0 .

Two similar samples are defined with two sets of mechanical characteristics ; the first sample is supposed to be almost perfectly cured (at 98 %) that corresponds to the area n°1 (center point of the cylinder) pointed in Fig. 3. However, such cured samples stay ideal and do not correspond to the industrial cured resin, rather cured at lower levels that could reach 80 %. So, a second sample is defined with a set of mechanical characteristics corresponding to a degree of cure of 80 %. For both sets, mechanical characteristics are taken from ABAQUS® simulation results presented in section 3, they are presented in table 3. Some other characteristics (Γ_0 , s , C_0) have been taken from the literature [18], [19].

A column of 31 layers of ambient matrix has also been simulated. Material properties after curing at ambient temperature, for each layer, are deduced from Fig. 8 to 10, reproducing the gradient of properties in E , ρ_0 , C_L , ν , Y_0 along the sample thickness, in axis direction.

At last, simulations have extended to cylindrical samples, in 2D axisymmetrical geometry, as thick as the previous columns, but with a radius of 1,5 cm, respectively for an homogeneous and 31 layers cases in elastic regime.

4.3. Simulation results

Numerical results obtain with 500 and 5000 cubic elements along the 3 cm thick column were almost similar, at least for the main features (time of arrival at the free surface, pressure load transmitted in the first element). Thus, a 500 elements mesh has been adopted for the rest of the works. For all simulations, the resituted pressure loads in the first element were in agreement with the original input load and from one simulation to another. Then, observations were focused on the free surface velocity and particularly on the time of flight (i.e. time taken by the pulse for going from the loaded surface to the free surface) and the velocity amplitude.

Fig. 12 shows the free surface velocity versus time for degrees of cure of 80 %, 98 % and a gradient cured with 31 layers between 98 % and 72 %, at ambient temperature for the column case. As expected, since the higher degree of cure, and thus Young modulus and density, the higher material

velocity has been observed. So, the time of flight is shorter for the sample having a degree of cure of 98%, longer for the one of 80 % and intermediate for the 31 layers sample. It is respectively 12, 12.7 and 12.1 μs . The higher the degree of cure, the lower the velocity amplitude is, this is explained by the effect of the cure on the mechanical impedance, particularly well illustrated in a “pressure vs material velocity” plane (also called shock polar). The shock polars in Fig. 13 give the material velocity in a medium for a given pressure and they can be obtained from Rankine-Hugoniot conservation equations [22]. For an pressure load of 7 MPa, the material velocity in the sample is respectively 2.7 m/s and 2.6 m/s for cured resins at 98 % and 80 %. The value obtained for the layered resins is approximately 2.5 m/s. The rear surface velocity is about the double of the material velocity within the sample, when the shock does not meet any decay [23], so the results showed in Fig. 12 are slightly under-estimated but consistent.

Although this first approach seems to be encouraging, these simulations do not correspond exactly to laser induced shock experiments but rather than to Hopkinson bar experiments that are hardly automatable and cannot be performed in situ in a warm resin in curing process. Moreover, shock propagation on a rod does not represent what could be observed in a plane surface of a thick sample. Indeed, edge effects [24] occurring back to the shock front are not considered in a column simulation and are in reality of a major importance because of the decay they can provoke.

Laser experiments own many advantages, among them : accuracy, easiness of monitoring, fastness of execution, contactless [25]. Simulations have been carried out on a cylindrical sample of a 98 % cured resin released at ambient temperature. A pressure pulse define at section 4.1 is applied on the centre of the upper face of this vertical cylinder of resin. Energy carried by photons is absorbed by the material and this last sees its internal energy increase suddenly. When the density of power deposited on the material is important enough, the target material is sublimed, provoking the ejection of a plasma that creates a throttle in the material and thus a shock wave. Such an irradiation is said in “ablation regime”. When the density of power is weaker, the material just undergoes heat that results in a thermo-elastic stress due to dilation. This stress propagates

as a “elastic shock” in the material. This is the “thermo-elastic regime” and this is the situation adopted in this work, since the purpose is to provide a non destructive tool. The pressure is applied on a circular area of 1.5 mm radius, corresponding to a laser focused beam spot, although the shock duration has been kept similar to previous experiments and does not represent what obtained by a laser irradiation. The computed free surface velocity is shown on Fig. 13, dark lines, and is different to what obtained for the column case in Fig. 12. Although the time of flight seems to be coherent, the velocity amplitude has become down to 0.25 m/s, that requires a sensitive enough equipment with a frequency response of several hundreds of MHz [26].

This loss in free surface velocity is explained by hydrodynamic effects caused by release waves occurring on the edge of the pressure load and propagating behind the shock front, towards the axis of symmetry. The sound velocity is higher behind the shock front, then, these release waves propagate faster than the shock itself, catch it and reduce it strongly. Once these edge waves cross the axis of symmetry, they meet each other and induce a traction wave that explain the negative peak of velocity follows the first positive peak, at the free surface (Fig. 14).

In order to overcome this limitation, a wider pressure loading, on a disk of 3 mm of radius, has been considered, which delays the edge effects. The resulting free surface velocity is plotted in grey lines on Fig. 13. The velocity peak, almost 1 m/s, is much more higher, about four times more, than the one computed with the radius of 1.5 mm. Although the local aspect in non destructive evaluation turns in fail-soft mode, the free surface velocity becomes observable.

The pressure fields pictures shown in Fig. 15 are taken from the simulation, with a load radius of 1.5 mm, for a homogeneous sample, at 6, 8, 12, 14, 16 and 18 μs .

Red and blue colours respectively point out compression and traction. 6 μs after impact, a compression wave is propagating towards the free surface, followed by a tensile wave provoked by edge effects. At 8 μs , waves are reflected against the side of the sample. A first area of intensified tensile appears at the crossing of this reflection and the incident tensile wave. At 12 μs , the reflected waves are crossing the axis of propagation, creating another area of tensile, that propagates towards the free

surface. At 14 μ s, both compression and tensile waves are reflected against the free surface, respectively in tensile and compression waves. These waves cross other tensile waves, provoking localised tensile areas.

These tensile stresses could be used for testing the toughness of materials and assemblies [28]. Obviously, the shock energy can be monitored so that the amplitude of the free surface velocity be higher and attest the signature of an induced damage. Such experiments would help determining the damage threshold of the resin.

5. Conclusions

This preliminar calculations have showed that impact simulation, of bars or laser induced shocks, could lead to determine the degree of cure of a resin released at ambient temperature, by an inverse approach. This numerical work is a predictive step for dimensionning the experimental setup of non destructive experiments that could characterise the gradient of properties within the material :

By a single shot, the response in free surface velocity could be compared to the numerical one, and thus the average state could be estimated. Section 3 showed that the state of the material at room temperature could be described by a function with one parameter that would be deduced from the experiment / simulation comparison.

By increasing the laser induced shock amplitude, it would be possible to determine the damage threshold of a thick matrix.

Table 1: Cure kinetics coefficients of the LY556 epoxy resin system for the Kamal and Sourour model.

A_1 (s ⁻¹)	A_2 (s ⁻¹)	E_1 (kJ/mol)	E_2 (kJ/mol)
1339879.17	21042820.69	69.14	72.62
m = 1 ; n = 2			

Table 2: Temperature dependency of diffusion parameter b and final degree of conversion α_f for the LY556 epoxy resin system.

b	α_f
$b = 7.1588 \text{ E-4} \cdot T(^{\circ}\text{K}) - 2.2816 \text{ E-1}$	$\alpha_f = 4.0646 \text{ E-3} \cdot T(^{\circ}\text{K}) - 8.2434 \text{ E-1}$

Table 3. Sets of mechanical parameters used in simulations :

Degree of curing	80 %	98 %
ρ_0 (g/cm ³)	1.251	1.254
E (MPa)	23.13	28.19
v	0.432	0.425
C_0	1917	1988
s	1.47	1.47
Γ_0	0.8	0.8
Y_0 (MPa)	8.08	9.89

Fig. 1: Diffusion factor impact on the Kamal and Sourour autocatalytic model (100°C isothermal curing).

Fig. 2 Temperature history during the curing in a 30 mm thick epoxy; comparison between model and thermocouple probes inside of the epoxy matrix (LY556 epoxy resin, ramp 3°C/min and 100°C plateau).

Fig. 3. Degree of cure gradients predicted within a 30 mm thick epoxy matrix during the 3°C/min ramp and 100°C plateau.

Fig. 4. Epoxy matrix sample for a shear test done at 125°C. The white spot was used for video-control of shear strain evolution. A plastic strain is observed after return at room temperature.

Fig. 5. Local shear stress strain evolutions versus temperature.

Fig. 6. Epoxy Elastic shear modulus change with temperature.

Fig. 7. Elastic shear modulus and degree of conversion gradients along the axis of the cylinder block of epoxy, after cooling down to room temperature.

Fig. 8. Epoxy Elastic shear modulus change with temperature.

Fig. 9. Yield shear stress change along the axis of the cylinder block of epoxy, after cooling down to room temperature.

Fig. 10. Failure shear stress change along the axis of the cylinder block of epoxy, after cooling down to room temperature.

Fig. 11. Pressure loading definition.

Fig. 12. Material velocity at the free surface computed for 80 % degree of cure, 98 % degree of cure and 31 layers samples at ambient temperature.

Fig. 13. Shock polars in elastic regime for homogeneous epoxy resins respectively cured at 98 % and 80 %, and cured epoxy resin with a gradient varying as computed in section 3.

Fig. 14. Material velocity at the free surface computed for 98 % degree of cure and 31 layers samples at ambient temperature. Radius of impact is respectively 1.5 mm in dark lines and 3 mm in grey lines.

Fig. 15. Hydrodynamic pressure field in the 3 cm thick epoxy heterogeneous sample after a laser induced shock wave in a disk of 3 mm of radius on the top surface, after, respectively from top-left to down-right : 6, 8, 12, 14, 16 and 18 μs.

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